

THE EFFECT OF EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING APPROACH ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND REFLECTIVE SKILLS OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS IN SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of experiential learning approach on the academic achievements and reflective skills of Grade 8 students in science. The study was conducted at Pangutaran National High School-Main, Schools Division of Sulu, during the school year 2023-2024. The pretest-posttest quasi-experimental control group and descriptive design was used in this study in determining the effect of experiential learning approach on the academic achievement and reflective skills of the students in science. The researcher-made achievement test, and reflective skills questionnaire were utilized as instrument for gathering the data. The Mean, Standard Deviation, Test of Normality, and Mann-Whitney U test at 0.05 level of significance were the statistical tools used to treat the data. The findings revealed that: (1) The level of academic achievement of grade 8 students taught using experiential learning approach was very satisfactory, (2) The level of academic achievement of grade 8 students taught using conventional method did not meet expectation, (3) The level of reflective skills of the grade 8 students in force and motion topic using experiential learning approach is generally high. The students consistently engaged in self-reflection, demonstrating high level of reflective skills, and (4) There was a significant difference in the academic achievement between grade 8 students taught using experiential learning approach and those taught using conventional method.

Key words: *Experiential Learning Approach, Conventional Method, Academic Achievement, Reflective Skills, Force and Motion*

INTRODUCTION

The K to 12 curriculum paved the way for developing the innovation, reflective, collaborative, and critical thinking skills of the learners. Teachers opted to adapt different teaching strategies to cater the diverse needs of the learners. One of the strategies that are widely used by teachers in teaching Sciences is the experiential learning approach. Experiential learning approach involves students in a complex understanding rather than surface learning and enable students to transfer knowledge better. Moreover, activities and environments associated in experiential learning such as experiments and laboratories, are the primary example of how experiential learning acts as a bridge on developing the skills of the students, and encouraging them to actively engage to the subject matter. However, despite the implementation of teaching strategies, there are still some students who did not understand the concept or scientific phenomenon.

An existing problem among the students in the Philippines is the low academic achievements. In the Program for International Students Assessment results (PISA, 2018), Philippines has been ranked 76th among 78 PISA-Performing countries worldwide. Philippines has the lowest mean score in science (357/600), mathematics (353/600), and reading (340/600). It is noted that the insufficient access to quality science education and resources are the major factor contributing to the low academic achievements of students. Moreover, it is reported that not all schools in the Philippines have access to adequate science material, including laboratory equipment and up-to-date textbooks which can hinder students' hands-on learning experiences and practical understanding of scientific concept (PISA, 2018). Additionally, modular distance learning or no face-to-face classes caused by pandemic is also considered as factor on students' low academic achievements. It leads students to be less motivated in class resulting to their low adaptability and low comprehension towards the discussion. As result, students fail to learn scientific phenomenon on a certain topic, and unable them to connect theories and knowledge they have learned in the classroom to real world situations.

According to Wang et al. (2012) as cited in Bernardo (2021), school characteristics have a significant influence on students' scientific literacy. Certain school characteristics, namely school standing, having libraries and laboratories, good relationship between students and teachers, and funding for teacher training were associated with higher science literacy score. Moreover, Hammerstein et al. (2021) also reported that pandemic shows a negative effect on student achievement, specifically in younger students with low socioeconomic status. In connection to that, teaching strategies such as experiential learning can be used to improve the certain problem. Bradberry and Maio (2019) confirmed that Experiential Learning Approach benefits primarily the students. It gives students a practical experience for their confidence as they prepare and make decisions about their future career paths. Additionally, Rukhsana et al. (2022) stated that experiential learning encourages students to think, investigate, ask questions, and make decisions.

The Department of Education has implemented the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, in line with the Republic Act No. 10533. Specifically, R.A No. 10533, Section

5 entitled “Curriculum Development” stated that the curriculum shall be learner-centered, inclusive and developmentally appropriate. This act addresses the need for quality education by enhancing the curriculum and learner-centered type of education by the implementation of different teaching strategies and approaches to the learning process.

There are several studies conducted internationally that utilized experiential learning approach. However, none of those have been particular to the present study. To mention, Alkan (2016); Experiential learning; It’s effect on achievement and scientific process skill. Abu-Assab (2015); The Effect of Experiential Learning on improving the performance of EFL students. Abonyi and Okoli (2014); The Effects of the Experiential learning strategy on secondary school students’ achievement in biology. The aforementioned studies focused on English, Biology, and Scientific Skills, while the present studies focused on Physics and reflective skills of Grade 8 students.

The researcher also examined the local studies that are parallel to the present study in terms of research locale, research design, research instruments, and treatment. For instance, Taludjog (2016); The effects of experiential learning approach on the Academic Performance and Interest in Chemistry of grade 9; Dolotallas and Nagtalon (2015); The effects of Experiential Learning Approach on the student’s performance in Filipino; Agsalog (2019): The effect of experiential learning approach on the academic performance and motivation of grade 10 students. The studies mentioned were focused on different disciplines such as Chemistry 9, Filipino 10, and Physics 10, however the present study focuses in Physics for grade 8 students and reflective skills.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate and explore the effect of experiential learning approach in the academic achievements and reflective skills of grade 8 students in science. Moreover, this study intended to introduce the experiential learning approach to teaching and learning process, as it would make the discussion connected to the real-life situation.

Framework of the Study

This study is anchored on the Experiential Theory by David Kolb (1984). This theory explains about the four-stage process of learning that transforms experiences into an effective and valuable learning. The four-stage process of David Kolb’s Theory are concrete experiences, reflective observations, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. These stages involve Assessing information and Observing information; wherein the students have new experiences and interprets the it in a new way, watching others and developing new idea by observing one’s personal experiences, formulating theories to explain the Observation, and enable to use a theory in solving problems and in making decisions.

Another theory relevant to this study is the Cognitive Theory of Bruner (1961). The theory emphasized that learners construct their own knowledge for themselves, which means that the intellectual level is the extent to which the learners have given an appropriate instruction together with practice and experiences. This study is also

anchored on the Constructivist learning theory developed by John Dewey (1938). This theory explained the learning process whereby everything occurs within a social environment and knowledge is socially constructed and based on experiences. Thus, the students have created a new knowledge and ability to apply it to different situations.

Further, this study is anchored on the Reflective Cycle of Gibbs (1998) in terms of reflective skills. This cycle theorized a framework for reflective practice that presents the reflective model which encourage students to think, evaluate, and establish an action plan from their experiences. This cycle consists of six stages, namely: Description, Feelings, Evaluation, Analysis, Conclusion, and Action Plan.

Figure 2 shows the Conceptual model of the study. On the left side of the box is the independent variable which represents the effect of teaching Strategies. On the right box is the dependent variables which can be changed depending on how effective the independent variable used in the study.

Figure 2. Conceptual Model of the Study

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following problems to determine the effects of experiential learning approach on the academic achievements of the grade 8 students in science.

1. What is the academic achievement of the students using experiential learning approach?
2. What is the academic achievement of the students using conventional method?

3. What is the level of reflective skills of the students in developed lesson on force and motion using experiential learning approach?
4. Is there a significant difference on the academic achievements of the students using experiential learning approach and conventional method?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Pangutaran National High School-Main, located in Simbahan, Pangutaran Sulu. Pangutaran is a 4th class municipality located in the northwest part of the province of Sulu. The researcher employed simple random sampling design, specifically the fishbowl technique, in selecting the 60 participants to provide the sample size with equal chances. This means that the researcher collects the names of the students from three selected section of Grade 8. The names were randomly picked by the researcher, and the selected twenty names were the official participants of the study. Hence, 30 randomly selected students were assigned to the control group and the remaining 30 students to the experimental group. The students in the experimental group were equally paired with the students in the control group.

Proper Protocol in gathering the data were observed by the researcher. The researcher developed a survey-questionnaire and a lesson together with the achievement test, and the aforementioned instruments was validated by the panel of experts for accuracy, validity, and reliability. Letter from the principal of the Pangutaran National High School-Main were sought for approval of the conduct of the study, and the researcher was requesting to the panel of experts and principal about the conduct of the study. After requesting, the given procedure was followed. Moreover, proper research ethics was strictly observed and followed by the researcher.

This study utilized a researcher-made test-questionnaire as an instrument in gathering the data. The researcher developed a 30-items pre-test and post-test questionnaire and give it to the chosen respondents. The said Test-Questionnaire is based on the learning competencies, and guided with the Table of Specification (TOS) with the domains of bloom's taxonomy. It contains 9 items for remembering, 9 for understanding, 5 applying, 4 analyzing, 2 evaluating, and 1 creating. The test-questionnaire contains a question and the choices, wherein the students encircled the choices below. The lesson and test questionnaire formulated by the researcher was be validated by the panel of experts.

Further, the researcher also utilized a researcher-made survey-questionnaire in gathering the information for the level of reflective skills of the students. The survey-questionnaire contains 15 statements together with rating scale where the respondent will just mark check in the space given after the statement and below the chosen rating scale that fitted to their answers.

The research instruments undergo checking and critiquing by the panel of experts and english critic before the distribution for final conduct, to ensure the validity of the research instruments. Furthermore, the researcher also conducted a try-out and pilot

testing to grade 9 and grade 10 students of Pangutaran National High School to ensure the reliability of the instruments. After pilot testing, the data gathered from pilot testing was analyzed using the reliability test which obtained a Cronbach Alpha of 0.9 for survey questionnaire, and 0.6 for achievement test. Therefore, the research instruments were tested valid and reliable and the researcher may proceed to use the instruments for final conduct.

Development of the Lesson Plan

The development of the lesson for the Experiential Learning Approach begins with the planning of lesson. The topic were Force and Motion. The researcher utilized a K-12 teacher manual, learners guide, and internet sources in planning the lesson and activity. The features (5-Step) of Experiential Learning Approach by Pfeiffer and Jones (1985) was used as the model for designing the lesson.

I Exploration

This step involves engaging in hands-on activity that is directly related to the learning objective. It could be real-life situation, simulation, or experiment. The goal is to provide a tangible experience that serves as a foundation for learning.

II Sharing

This step encourages students to reflect and share their observation regarding on their concrete experiences. This step involves analyzing, and evaluating the experience, identifying patterns, and making connections to existing knowledge. Sharing and reflecting allows students to gain insight and extract meaningful lessons from the experience.

III Processing

This step takes the insights learned by the students from reflection and connect them to abstract concepts and theories, to develop deeper understanding of the concepts and their application in different contexts. The teacher together with the students discusses the activity and perform the lesson proper.

IV Generalizing

This step encourages students to apply their knowledge in new situation. This step involves active testing with the concepts learned through games, activity, and experiments. Students are encouraged to take risk, explore different approaches, and learn from the outcomes of their actions.

V Application

The final step emphasizes the importance of ongoing learning and improvement. Students are encouraged to reflect on the outcomes of their experimentation, identifies areas for improvement, and engage in further learning. This step emphasizes the iterative

nature of the experiential learning process, where each cycle builds upon the previous ones.

After writing, the developed lesson plan was presented and validated by the panel of experts to determine its accuracy, clarity, and appropriateness. The lesson plan was modified based from the suggestion of the panel of experts. The revised lesson was implemented to the Experimental Group only to test the Effectiveness of Experiential Learning Approach.

Table 1. Scoring guide for the effects of Experiential Learning Approach on the Academic Achievements of the Grade 8 Students in Science

The scoring procedure of this study is aligned with DepEd Order No. 8 Series of 2015, entitled “Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K–12 Basic Education Program.” This specific order issued several guidelines regarding the scoring procedure for studies and also outlines the principles and processes for assessing student learning.

Score Range	Grading Scale	Description	Remark	Qualifying Statement
27-30	90% - 100%	Passed	Outstanding	Advanced Proficiency in knowledge and skills.
23-26	85% - 89%	Passed	Very Satisfactory	Proficient in knowledge and skills.
19-22	80% - 84%	Passed	Satisfactory	Approaching Proficiency in knowledge and skills.
15-18	75%-79%	Failed	Fairly Satisfactory	Low Proficiency in knowledge and skills.
Below 15	75% Below	Failed	Did Not Meet Expectation	No Proficiency in knowledge and skills.

Table 2. Scoring Guide for the Level of Reflective Skills of the students in developed lesson on Force and Motion topic.

Scale	Range	Response	Qualifying Statement
5	4.20-5.00	Always	The students consistently engage in self-reflection, demonstrating very high level of reflective skills.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	The students frequently engage in self-reflection, demonstrating high reflective skills.
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes	The students occasionally engage in self-reflection, demonstrating moderate reflective skills
2	1.8-2.59	Rarely	The students infrequently engage in self-reflection, demonstrating limited reflective skills.
1	1-1.79	Never	The students never engage in self-reflection demonstrating lack of reflective skills.

The data were treated with the appropriate statistical tools for analysis.

For problem number 1, 2, 3, the mean and standard deviation was used to determine the level of the academic achievements of the grade 8 students who were taught with experiential learning approach and those who were taught with conventional method.

For problem number 4, the Shapiro-Wilk test assumption of normality test was first used to determine the normality of the data. further, after the test of normality, the Mann Whitney U test was used as non-parametric test to determine the significant difference in the academic achievements of the grade 8 students who were taught with experiential learning approach and those with conventional method.

This study delimited only on the effects of experiential learning approach on the academic achievements and reflective skills of the grade 8 students in science. This study specifically focuses on the test of effectiveness of the experiential learning approach on the achievement of grade 8 students in Force and Motion topic.

RESULTS

Table 3 shows the pre-test and post-test achievement scores of the grade 8 students for both experimental group and control group.

Table 3. *Academic Achievement of grade 8 students in Science*

Level of Proficiency	Range of Scores	Experimental Group				Control Group			
		Pretest		Post-test		Pretest		Post-test	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
O	27-30	0	0%	8	26.7%	0	0%	0	0%
VS	23-26	0	0%	22	73.3%	0	0%	0	0%
S	19-22	2	6.7%	0	0%	0	0%	5	16.7%
FS	15-18	4	13.3%	0	0%	3	10%	12	40%
DNME	Below 15	24	80%	0	0%	27	90%	13	43.3%
	Total	30	100%	30	100%	30	100%	30	100%
Mean		12.73		25.80		10.57		14.80	
SD		3.383		1.80		2.897		3.671	

Legend:

O – Outstanding

VS – Very Satisfactory

S – Satisfactory

FS – Fairly Satisfactory

DNME – Did Not Meet Expectation

Table 4. *Test of normality for the post-test scores of the students*

	Group	Shapiro-Wilk Test		
		Statistic	Df	P
Pretest	Control	0.892	30	0.005
	Experimental	0.906	30	0.012
Post-test	Control	0.872	30	0.002
	Experimental	0.914	30	0.019

Table 5. Mann-Whitney U test in computation of the academic achievement of grade 8 students in science between experimental group and control group.

	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	Test Statistic		
					Pretest	Post-test	
Pretest	Experimental	30	36.53	1096.00	Mann-Whitney U Wilcoxon W Z	269.000	0.000
	Control	30	24.47	734.00		734.000	465.000
	Total	60				-2.695	-6.693
Post-test	Experimental	30	45.50		Asymp. Sig. (2 tailed)	0.007	0.000
	Control	30	15.00	1365.00			
	Total	60		465.00			

Table 6. The level of Reflective Skills of Grade 8 students using Experiential Learning Approach

Reflective Skills	Mean	Std. d.	Ver. Des.
1. I enjoy performing activities in exploration process.	4.66	0.90	Always
2. I love to share and discuss my observation to my classmates.	4.37	0.99	Always
3. I can identify the positive and negative consequences in my previous activities.	3.73	0.69	Often
4. I automatically formulate ideas based from my observation of the activities.	4.43	0.81	Always
5. I automatically identify what should I do to improve the activities.	4.63	0.71	Always
6. I seek feedbacks from my teacher and classmate to check my ideas based from activities.	4.53	0.73	Always
7. I find it easy to identify my weaknesses and strengths through reflection.	4.50	0.68	Always
8. I can express my thoughts and insights clearly when reflecting my experiences in an activity.	4.30	0.65	Always
9. I am able to meet the learning competencies in the activity through reflection.	4.53	0.62	Always
10. I am able to connect my learning experience to my future goals.	4.90	0.30	Always

11. I am able to solve scientific problem from reflecting the knowledge I learned.	4.20	0.84	Always
12. I love engaging in self-reflection to understand insights in the previous activity.	4.97	0.18	Always
13. I compare and contrast theories to gain a broader understanding from my activities.	4.80	0.40	Always
14. I regularly take time to think deeply about the concepts I learned during class activity.	4.83	0.46	Always
15. I feel confident to make decision due to reflecting previous observation from activities.	4.77	0.56	Always
Overall	4.55	0.71	Always

Legend:

4.20-5.00 Always, 3.40-4.19 Often, 2.60-3.39 Sometimes, 1.80-2.59 Rarely, 1-1.79 Never

DISCUSSION

The data presented in Table 3 revealed that the experimental group had obtained higher mean scores. However, in pre-test phase, the students in experimental group obtained below 75 or did not meet expectation. This indicates that the students at this level have low proficiency in knowledge and skills in the given topic. Moreover, it can also be gleaned from the table that the mean score of the experimental group in the post-test had improved to *very satisfactory* level. After the experiential learning approach was implemented, the mean score for the post-test in experimental group significantly increased to 25.80. This improvement suggests that the experiential learning approach had a positive effect on the academic achievements of grade 8 students in force and motion topic.

Furthermore, there were 8 students (26.7%) identified as *outstanding*, and 22 students (73.3%) as *very satisfactory*. The data show that the score of students in experimental group were clustered at *very satisfactory* level. The results revealed that experiential learning approach really took place. It helps to improve the students' achievement level. Their participation in the learning process through different activities reveals that they have developed more understanding of the concepts which help retain more information. They were able to recall and apply this information better in real life situation than the control group.

The findings of the present study collaborate with the findings of Taludjog (2016), which revealed that the academic performance of students taught with an experiential learning approach is higher compared with those who are taught with the conventional method. Moreover, the study of Abonyi and Okoli (2014) is also parallel to the present study, revealing that the students in experimental group have a higher post-test score than those students in control group.

On the other hand, the control group obtained a low mean score in both pre-test and post-test as shown in the table 3. It obtained 10.57 mean score in the pre-test which indicates that it *did not meet expectation*. This means that the students at pre-test level have low proficiency in knowledge and skills in force and motion topic. Parallel to the experimental group, the mean score for the post-test in the control group also improved to 14.80 but with the description of *did not meet expectation*. Although there was an improvement, the increase was not significantly observed. This improvement suggests that the conventional method had no effect on the academic achievements of grade 8 students in force and motion topic.

The researcher observed that the below-average proficiency performance of the students in control group may be due to the lack of interactive classroom activities, which enable them to be less engaged with the lesson and topic. The use of examples, illustrations, and drawings in modulating the lesson does not capture their attention to focus, which results to their low academic achievement in the post-test. Significantly, the absence of teaching approach being used by the teachers has contributed to the low academic achievement of the students in control group.

The major results showed that the achievements of the students in experimental group and control group were comparable. The students in the experimental group were more proficient in knowledge and skills in force and motion topic than those in control group. This finding connotes that the experiential learning approach is effective in improving the academic achievement of grade 8 students in science compared to conventional method.

As gleaned from Table 4, the result in Shapiro-Wilk shows that the experimental group obtained 0.012 for the pre-test and 0.019 for the post-test. While the control group obtained 0.005 for the pre-test and 0.002 for the post-test, this can be interpreted as meaning that the data from the experimental group and control group for both the pre-test and post-test does not meet the assumption of normality. This suggests that the use of the analysis of covariance as a parametric test to analyze the comparison of both groups is insignificant. Therefore, the researcher utilizes the Mann-Whitney U test as an alternative non-parametric test to determine the effect of an experiential learning approach on the academic achievement of grade 8 students.

As gleaned from Table 5, the mean rank in the pre-test of the experimental group (36.53) is higher than the mean rank of the control group (24.47), which indicates that students taught with experiential learning have an initial advantage in academic achievement. This has been supported by the sum of rank, with the experimental group totaling 1096.00 compared to 734.00 for the control group. In the post-test phase, the mean rank for the experimental group increased to 45.00 while the control group decreased to 15.00. The widened gap in the sum of ranks at 1365.00 for the experimental group and 465.000 for the control group suggested a continuous positive effect of experiential learning in teaching and improving the academic achievement of the student over time compared to conventional methods.

The Mann-Whitney U test indicated a significant difference between the two groups at both assessment points, with values of 269.00 and 0.000 for the post-test. The subsequent Wilcoxon W statistics showed a distribution shift towards a more significant effect of experiential learning, with values of 734.000 for the pretest and 465.000 for the post-test. The Z score was also in favor of experiential learning, with values of -2.695 for the pretest and -6.693 for the post-test. The asymptotic significance values in the pretest were 0.007 and 0.000 for the post-test, which both have a statistically significant difference.

Based on the results provided by the Mann-Whitney U test, Wilcoxon W statistics, and asymptotic significance values for the pre-test and post-test stages, the null hypothesis, which stated there is no significance difference in academic achievement between two groups is *rejected*. This rejection supports the conclusion that the experiential learning approach has a significant positive impact on the academic achievement of grade 8 students compared to the conventional teaching method

The findings of the present study agree with the findings of Abonyi and Okoli (2014), stated that implementing an experiential learning strategy in the lesson would improve the academic achievement of the students. It can be concluded that teaching with the use of an experiential learning strategy would enhance the skills and knowledge of the students through group activities, hands-on experimentation, and academic performance.

Furthermore, the result of this study is also strengthened by the study conducted by Hafeez (2022), which highlighted the comparison of game-based learning with the traditional learning method. It showed that game-based learning strategy is more effective learning strategy as compared to the traditional learning strategy while also the learners' engagement level increased more in the game- based learning strategy,

Hence, game based learning is a form of experiential learning which also offers the learners first-hand learning experiences, like the experiential learning approach.

As shown in table 6, the overall mean and majority of the responses of grade 8 students towards the level of reflective skills assessment were *Always*. This indicates that students taught using experiential learning approach consistently engage in self-reflection, demonstrating a high level of reflective skills.

Moreover, among the 15 statements, the items with the top 5 highest mean were as follows: *The students love engaging in self-reflection to understand insights from the previous activity* (4.97). *The students were able to connect their learning experience to their future goals* (4.90). *The students regularly take time to think about the concepts they learned during class activity* (4.83). *The students were able to compare and contrast theories to gain a broader understanding from their activities* (4.80). Lastly, *the students feel confident to make decision due to reflecting previous observation from their activities* (4.77).

The students involved in experiential learning responses to the statements with high degree of positive respond towards the effect of experiential learning towards their reflective skills. These responses are related to the students' skills developed during the implementation of experiential learning approach. These present findings agreed with the study of Abu-Assab (2015) which states that the experiential learning approach make the students active learner since it promotes their thinking, social skills, and able to connect their future goals based on their experiences. Furthermore, these responses from the students strongly supports the statement of Wurdinger (2005) that the "outcomes of the learning process are varied and often unpredictable" and "learners play a critical role in assessing their own learning". Generally, as shown in the table, the grade 8 students had a high level of reflective skills in force and motion topic using the experiential learning approach. This shows that the students were certainly able to reflect their learning experience to grasp deeper understanding of the concept to enrich their knowledge in force and motion topic.

According to Moon (1990), "reflective practice can be enhanced through engaging in systematic and structured reflection activities, fostering deeper understanding and self-awareness". Moreover, the promotion of reflective skills aligns seamlessly with the experiential learning approach, as emphasized by Kolb (1984). By engaging in hands-on experiences, such as practical activities, students have concrete experiences to reflect upon.

According to Hatton and Smith (1995), "effective feedback and facilitation contribute significantly to the development of reflective skills of the students". Subsequently, the facilitation of reflective skills as emphasized by Hatton and Smith (1995), complements the experiential learning approach. In the context of the present study, feedbacks and guidance play a pivotal role during the reflective and sharing phase of the cycle, reinforcing the connections between exploration phase and Processing phase. This integration ensures a stronger experiential learning process.

Conclusions

1. The experiential learning approach is effective in improving the academic achievements of grade 8 students in science.
2. The conventional method is less effective in improving the academic achievements of grade 8 students in science.
3. The integration of Experiential Learning Approach in teaching science 8 specifically Force and Motion topic can improve the academic achievement of students. It can help develop proficiency in knowledge and skills in science.
4. The use of Experiential Learning Approach could develop and enhance the reflective skills of the students.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that the students be exposed to experiential learning approach to enhance their ability to connect their knowledge and conceptual understanding to real-world applications.
 2. Science teachers should utilize the experiential learning approach to support the development and improvement of students' academic achievement and performance in science.
 3. It is suggested that teachers are encouraged to utilize the experiential learning approach in designing the lesson in science to encourage active learning and engagement among students.
 4. Students should be exposed to experiential learning approach to enhance their reflective skills and further reflect learning for a quality concrete and abstract knowledge.
 5. School Administrators should introduce the used of experiential learning approach in teaching not only Science but other subject areas.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study diligently addresses the appropriate ethics and concerns regarding the authority to conduct the study. The researcher of this study profoundly approaches the thesis adviser for the accuracy of the manuscripts, and strictly follows the suggestions made by the panel of experts during the correction phase. Moreover, the researcher also appreciates the importance of conducting research with commitment to uphold research excellence, data confidentiality, originality, while ethically safeguarding the rights and well-being of all individuals involved in the study.

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